

secrBVN - simulation of spatially explicit capture-recapture with bivariate normal home ranges

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The small package **secrBVN** is used to evaluate the performance of SECR estimators when home ranges are bivariate normal (BVN) or uniform (flat-topped) ellipses. We assume detection hazard is directly proportional to home range utilisation (activity). Code to use **secrBVN** for the simulations of Efford (in prep.) is provided in the Appendix.

The key user-visible functions are `simpopn.bvn`, `plotpopn.bvn`, `simcapt.bvn`, `runEllipseSim`, `simsum`, `simplot` and `anisotropic.fit`.

Generating and plotting elliptical home ranges

`simpopn.bvn` is a wrapper for the `secr` function `sim.popn` that adds attributes specifying a bivariate normal home range shape, size and orientation for each individual. By default, shape and size are the same for all individuals, but a mechanism is provided to vary them individually (see Heterogeneous elliptical home ranges).

First, load the package.

```
library(secrBVN)
```

```
## Warning: package 'secr' was built under R version 3.5.1
```

```
simfolder <- "c:/density communication/noncircularity/paper/simulations/"
runall <- FALSE # skip lengthy simulations
```

```
tempgrid <- make.grid(nx = 10, ny = 10)
par(mfrow = c(2,4), mar = c(2,2,2.6,2), xpd = TRUE)
for (i in 1:4) {
  s2xy <- 25^2 * c(1/i, i)
  random.pop <- simpopn.bvn(s2xy = s2xy, core = tempgrid, buffer = 100, D = 1)
  plotpopn.bvn(random.pop, col = 'lightblue')
  mtext(side=3, line=1.5, i)
}
for (i in 1:4) {
  s2xy <- 25^2 * c(1/i, i)
  aligned.pop <- simpopn.bvn(s2xy = s2xy, core = tempgrid, buffer = 100, D = 1, theta = -1)
  plotpopn.bvn(aligned.pop, col = 'lightblue')
}
```


Fig. 1. Elliptical home ranges with varying ratio of major to minor axes as shown. Upper row oriented randomly and independently, lower row with shared random orientation ('randomly aligned').

Simulating elliptical detection data

Generating detection histories

Normally in **secr** we use `sim.caphist` to generate capture histories, but that is limited to circular detection functions. The **secrBVN** function `simcapt.bvn` is a partial replacement for `sim.caphist` that models detection with a bivariate normal. Specifically, the cumulative hazard of detection is a constant times the bivariate normal probability density at the detector. The constant is $\lambda_0 2\pi\sigma_X\sigma_Y$. The user provides a 'popn' object that includes the BVN parameter values $(\sigma_x^2, \sigma_y^2, \theta)$ for each animal (row), as generated above by `simpopn.bvn`. The constant scales the BVN density so that the maximum hazard is λ_0 .

The preceding paragraph describes the default behaviour of `simcapt.bvn`. If `type = uniform` is selected then a uniform (flat-topped) elliptical home range is simulated. The uniform probability of detection within the ellipse is controlled by `g0`, not `lambda0`.

Wrapper function to generate BVN data and fit SECR model

The function `runEllipseSim` is a wrapper for the preceding steps (`simpopn.bvn`, `simcapt.bvn`) that also fits a standard (circular) SECR model with `secr.fit`¹. The default population has a fixed number of individuals within the rectangular buffered area around the detectors (`Ndist = 'fixed'`).

For this example we use a 6×6 grid of binary proximity detectors with 50 metre spacing. The code in **secrBVN** does not allow for competition among detectors (secr detector type 'multi') or other other secr detector types. A density of 4/ha gives exactly 169 animals in the buffered area. Conditional likelihood is used for speed; the default `extractfn = derived` is compatible with both `CL = TRUE` and `CL = FALSE`. The 200-m buffer allows for the longest ranges ($\sigma_y = 50$ m).

```
tr <- make.grid(6, 6, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simrandomBVN36 <- vector('list', 4)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  simrandomBVN36[[i]] <- runEllipseSim (nrepl = 500, sigmaX, sigmaY, buffer = 200,
    ncores = 20, traps = tr, lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN',
    CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = list(distribution = 'binomial'))
}
```

The **secrBVN** function `simplot` is used to summarize the results

```
par(xpd = FALSE, mar = c(4,4,4,4))
simplot(list(BVN = simrandomBVN36))
```

¹An elliptical SECR model also may be fitted - see Anisotropic home ranges.

Fig. 2. Relative bias of density estimated by fitting circular SECR detection model to elliptical data, with 95% confidence limit for simulated values.

Next print a summary of the simulation results. There is no apparent effect of range elongation itself on the bias of the estimates.

```
simsum(list(BVN = simrandomBVN36))
```

```
## $BVN
##      av.nCH   RB   RSE rRMSE  COV
## [1,] 42.184 0.020 0.140 0.149 0.940
## [2,] 42.942 0.019 0.139 0.146 0.934
## [3,] 43.950 0.019 0.139 0.143 0.946
## [4,] 44.704 0.013 0.139 0.142 0.948
```

The Appendix has many other examples.

Heterogeneous elliptical home ranges

`simpopn.bvn` by default generates a population with equal-sized home ranges. The size and elongation of each range may be varied by providing a user-defined function as the argument `s2xy`:

```
tr <- make.grid(6,6, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
rs2xy <- function(N, scale = 25) {
  aspectratio <- 1 + runif(N) * 3
  cbind(scale^2 / aspectratio, scale^2 * aspectratio)
}
pop <- simpopn.bvn(s2xy = rs2xy, core = tr, buffer = 100, D = 1)
par(mfrow = c(1,1), mar = c(4,4,4,4), xpd = TRUE)
plotpopn.bvn(pop, col = 'grey')
```


Heterogeneous populations may also be simulated in `runEllipseSim` by passing a function as the argument `'sigmaX'`.

```
sims <- runEllipseSim (10, sigmaX = rs2xy, buffer = 200, ncores = 2,  
                      traps = tr, g0 = 0.2, D = 4, type = 'uniform')
```

Anisotropic home ranges: a partial solution

In principle, we can deal with elongated ranges by replacing Euclidean distances with distances in a space transformed to render home ranges circular (Murphy et al. 2016). The transformation compresses home ranges along their major axis. The transformation uses two parameters: ψ_A for the shared orientation measured in radians and ψ_R for the compression ratio ($\psi_R \geq 1$; $\psi_R = 1$ corresponds to no compression). The parameter ψ_A (`psiA`) corresponds to the argument `theta` used by `simpopn.bvn`. Thanks to Ben Augustine for pointing out the `geoR` function `coords.aniso` that lets us do this (Ribeiro and Diggle 2018)².

The method does not work if the detector array is strictly linear (2-D data are required to estimate the orientation and compression parameters). It is tested in the Appendix on simulated data from a hollow square array.

Distances in transformed space

The code uses a user-defined distance function that computes a Euclidean distance in the transformed space. In this version both transformation parameters are estimated (cf Murphy et al. 2016). Transformation parameters are handled in the undocumented `'miscparm'` feature of `secr.fit`. This allows supernumerary unmodelled parameters to be passed to the distance function. The parameters are included in the vector of coefficients (beta parameters) over which the likelihood is maximised. 'Unmodelled' here means that the

²The package `intamap` (Pebesma et al. 2010) also offers anisotropic transformation in function `rotateAnisotropicData`.

parameter takes a single value for all animals, times and places. The link function is 'identity' for ψ_A and 'log' for $\psi_R - 1$.

```
anisodistfn <- function (xy1, xy2, mask) {
  if (missing(xy1)) return(character(0))
  xy1 <- as.matrix(xy1)
  xy2 <- as.matrix(xy2)
  miscparm <- attr(mask, 'miscparm')
  psiA <- miscparm[1] # anisotropy angle; identity link
  psiR <- 1 + exp(miscparm[2]) # anisotropy ratio; log link
  aniso.xy1 <- geoR::coords.aniso(xy1, aniso.pars = c(psiA, psiR))
  aniso.xy2 <- geoR::coords.aniso(xy2, aniso.pars = c(psiA, psiR))
  secr::edist(aniso.xy1, aniso.xy2) # nrow(xy1) x nrow(xy2) matrix
}
```

Example

Here is a simple application with oblique elliptical home ranges ($\theta = \pi/4$).

```
tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 25, hollow = TRUE, detector = 'proximity')
pop <- simpopn.bvn(s2xy = (25*c(0.5,2))^2, theta = pi/4, core = tr, buffer = 200,
  D = 4, Ndist = 'fixed')
CH <- simcapt.bvn(tr, pop, type = 'BVN', lambda = 0.4, noccasions = 5)

par(mfrow = c(1,1))
plot(CH, tracks = TRUE)
plotpopn.bvn(pop, border='grey', add = TRUE)
plot(tr, add = TRUE)
```

5 occasions, 105 detections, 44 animals

First we fit a naive circular model.

```
fit0 <- secr.fit(CH, buffer = 200, detectfn = 'HHN', trace = FALSE,
  details = list(distribution = 'binomial'))
predict(fit0)
```

```
##      link  estimate SE.estimate      lcl      ucl
## D      log  4.8304297  0.76476420  3.5485825  6.5753162
## lambda0 log  0.2560395  0.04965347  0.1756934  0.3731284
## sigma   log 29.0103269  2.44949833 24.5928405 34.2213038
```

Next, the model with transformation to isotropy.

```
details <- list(distribution = 'binomial', userdist = anisodistfn,
  miscparm = c(psiA = 0.5, psiR = 1.5)) # initial values
fit1 <- secr.fit(CH, buffer = 200, detectfn = 'HHN', trace = FALSE,
  details = details)
predict(fit1)
```

```
##      link  estimate SE.estimate      lcl      ucl
## D      log  4.3431775  0.78165950  3.0607831  6.1628643
## lambda0 log  0.3560631  0.06474752  0.2500341  0.5070546
## sigma   log 12.6289356  1.22771300 10.4426882 15.2728888
```

```
coef(fit1)
```

```
##      beta  SE.beta      lcl      ucl
## D      1.4686062  0.17854176  1.1186708  1.8185417
## lambda0 -1.0326474  0.18036593 -1.3861581 -0.6791367
```

```
## sigma    2.5359907 0.09698577 2.3459020 2.7260793
## psiA     0.8326161 0.05260764 0.7295070 0.9357252
## psiR     1.0842930 0.26650652 0.5619498 1.6066362
```

The estimated bearing is 47.71 degrees. The estimated aspect ratio is 3.96, (95% CI 2.75, 5.99).

Function to fit anisotropic model

The `secrBVN` function `anisotropic.fit` streamlines model fitting and does not require `anisodistfn` to be defined externally. Use it as you would use `secr.fit`. For example,

```
fit2 <- anisotropic.fit(CH, buffer = 200, detectfn = 'HHN', trace = FALSE,
  details = list(distribution = "binomial"))
predictAniso(fit2) # estimates of transformation parameters psiA (in degrees) and psiR
```

```
##      estimate SE.estimate      lcl      ucl
## psiA 47.70538   3.0141944 41.79767 53.613092
## psiR  3.95735   0.8023571  2.75409  5.986014
```

Fixed orientation

If the orientation is known then there are two solutions:

1. Re-write `anisodistfn` for `miscpar` of length 1, with hard-coded value for `psiA`, or
2. Fix the beta parameter corresponding to `psiA`.

Here we demonstrate (2), fixing `psiA` at $\pi/4$ (45 degrees). The `secr.fit` `details` argument `fixedbeta` is a vector of values, one per 'beta' parameter, using `NA` for each beta to be estimated. The first three beta parameters are for `D`, `lambda0` and `sigma`; the next two are for `psiA` and `psiR`. If you model `D`, `lambda0` or `sigma` there will be extra beta parameters, pushing `psiA` and `psiR` back.

```
fit3 <- anisotropic.fit(CH, buffer = 200, detectfn = 'HHN', trace = FALSE,
  details = list(distribution = "binomial", fixedbeta = c(NA,NA,NA,pi/4,NA)))
predictAniso(fit3) # estimate of psiR only
```

```
##      estimate SE.estimate      lcl      ucl
## psiA 45.000000          NA          NA          NA
## psiR  3.917419   0.8023285  2.718544  5.95264
```

```
predict(fit3)
```

```
##      link  estimate SE.estimate      lcl      ucl
## D      log  4.3220351  0.78072117  3.042020  6.1406526
## lambda0 log  0.3534778  0.06433671  0.248139  0.5035345
## sigma   log 12.7849783  1.24111272 10.574566 15.4574350
```

Inadequate data

Detectors in a straight line provide very little information with which to estimate ψ_A and ψ_R . Here is an example.

```
tr <- make.grid(100, 1, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity')
pop <- simpopn.bvn(s2xy = (25*c(0.5,2))^2, theta = pi/4, core = tr, buffer = 200,
  D = 4, Ndist = 'fixed')
CH <- simcapt.bvn(tr, pop, type = 'BVN', lambda = 0.4, nooccasions = 5)
```

```
fit4 <- anisotropic.fit(CH, buffer = 200, detectfn = 'HHN', trace = FALSE,
  details = list(distribution = "binomial"))
predictAniso(fit4) # estimates of transformation parameters psiA (in degrees) and psiR
```

```
##      estimate SE.estimate      lcl      ucl
## psiA 14.34527   4.677842  5.176867 23.513671
## psiR  4.73485   1.382208  2.850590  8.537651
```

```
predict(fit4)
```

```
##      link  estimate SE.estimate      lcl      ucl
## D      log  2.2160860  0.62881084  1.2844580  3.8234317
## lambda0 log  0.4139158  0.04828277  0.3295761  0.5198384
## sigma   log 15.0129592  0.93736540 13.2853026 16.9652850
```

(Perhaps the parameters are not strictly nonidentifiable).

Package limitations

This package has the limited goal of determining how range elongation affects estimates of density in simple SECR models, and these specific limitations:

1. Only binary proximity detectors are supported.
2. The spatial distribution of activity centres is assumed to be homogeneous Poisson.
3. Ellipses are specified using either 'sigmaX' and 'sigmaY' as separate arguments (`runEllipseSim`) or as a vector of the two values, squared ('s2xy' in `simpopn.bvn`). This is confusing but it's better at this point not to change.

References

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- Murphy, S. M., Cox, J. J., Augustine, B. C., Hast, J. T., Guthrie, J. M., Wright, J., McDermott, J., Maehr, S. C. and Plaxico, J. H. (2016) Characterizing recolonization by a reintroduced bear population using genetic spatial capture–recapture. *Journal of Wildlife Management* **80**, 1390–1407.
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- Ribeiro, P. J. Jr and Diggle, P. J. (2018) geoR: Analysis of Geostatistical Data. R package version 1.7-5.2.1. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=geoR>.

Appendix. Code for simulations of Efford (in prep)

```
library(secrBVN)
simfolder <- "c:/density communication/noncircularity/paper/simulations/"
nrepl <- 500
ncores <- 20 # for machine with at least 20 cores
runsim <- FALSE # change to TRUE to execute simulations
details <- list(distribution = 'binomial') # all simulations assume fixed N
```

Functions for heterogeneous aspect ratio.

```
# Uniform on 1-4
rs2xy <- function(N, scale = 25) {
  i <- 1 + runif(N) * 3
  cbind(scale^2 /i, scale^2 * i)
}
# 2 classes 1,4
rs2xy2 <- function(N, scale = 25, prob = c(0.5,0.5)) {
  i <- sample(c(1,4), size = N, replace = TRUE, prob = prob)
  cbind(scale^2 /i, scale^2 * i)
}
```

Main simulations

10 x 10 grid

Elongated ranges are oriented at random with respect to the grid (default `theta = NULL`).

```
tr <- make.grid(10,10, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simrandom100.3 <- vector('list', 6)
names(simrandom100.3) <- c(1:4, '1-4', '1,4')
simrandomBVN100.3 <- simrandom100.3
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr, theta = NULL,
  D = 4, CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details, seed = 347)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  # uniform
  args$type <- 'uniform'; args$g0 <- 0.2
  simrandom100.3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bvn
  args$type <- 'BVN'; args$lambda0 <- 0.4
  simrandomBVN100.3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  message('Completed aspect ratio', i)
}
# heterogeneous aspect ratio 1,4, uniform
args$type <- 'uniform'; args$sigmaX <- rs2xy
simrandom100.3[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
# heterogeneous aspect ratio 1,4, BVN
args$type <- 'BVN'; args$sigmaX <- rs2xy
simrandomBVN100.3[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
# heterogeneous aspect ratio 1,4, uniform
args$type <- 'uniform'; args$sigmaX <- rs2xy2
```

```

simrandom100.3[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
#heterogeneous aspect ratio 1,4, BVN
args$type <- 'BVN'; args$sigmaX <- rs2xy2; args$seed <- 347
simrandomBVN100.3[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

save(simrandom100.3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom100.3.RData'))
save(simrandomBVN100.3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100.3.RData'))

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom100.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100.3.RData'))

par(mfrow = c(1,1), mar = c(4,4,4,4), xpd = FALSE)
# select only first 4 scenarios for plotting
simplot(list(Uniform = simrandom100.3[1:4], BVN = simrandomBVN100.3[1:4]), legend = TRUE)

```



```

# tabulate all
simsum(list(Uniform = simrandom100.3, BVN = simrandomBVN100.3), compact = NULL, dec = 4)

```

```

## $Uniform
##           1           2           3           4           1-4           1,4
## av.npop   289.0000 289.0000 289.0000 289.0000 289.0000 289.0000
## av.nCH    121.0620 123.2520 126.3220 129.2880 124.7580 125.4240
## nvalid    500.0000 500.0000 500.0000 500.0000 500.0000 500.0000
## av.parmhat  3.9543  3.9404  3.9174  3.9005  3.9168  3.9210
## md.parmhat  3.9722  3.9454  3.9324  3.9116  3.9189  3.9181
## sd.parmhat  0.2829  0.2852  0.2760  0.2695  0.2689  0.2712
## RB         -0.0114 -0.0149 -0.0207 -0.0249 -0.0208 -0.0197
## seRB        0.0032  0.0032  0.0031  0.0030  0.0030  0.0030
## RSE         0.0686  0.0676  0.0662  0.0650  0.0669  0.0666

```

```

## seRSE      0.0001  0.0001  0.0001  0.0001  0.0001  0.0001
## rRMSE      0.0716  0.0728  0.0720  0.0718  0.0703  0.0706
## COV        0.9400  0.9320  0.9280  0.9000  0.9280  0.9380
##
## $BVN
##           1         2         3         4         1-4         1,4
## av.npop   289.0000 289.0000 289.0000 289.0000 289.0000 289.0000
## av.nCH    108.3260 109.4820 110.9340 112.0540 110.0220 109.9820
## nvalid    500.0000 500.0000 500.0000 500.0000 500.0000 500.0000
## av.parmhat 4.0257  4.0172  3.9958  3.9652  3.9895  3.9731
## md.parmhat 4.0378  4.0215  3.9992  3.9739  4.0094  3.9591
## sd.parmhat 0.3202  0.3280  0.3247  0.3100  0.3116  0.3089
## RB        0.0064  0.0043 -0.0011 -0.0087 -0.0026 -0.0067
## seRB      0.0036  0.0037  0.0036  0.0035  0.0035  0.0035
## RSE       0.0773  0.0769  0.0765  0.0762  0.0767  0.0767
## seRSE     0.0001  0.0001  0.0001  0.0001  0.0001  0.0001
## rRMSE     0.0802  0.0820  0.0811  0.0779  0.0779  0.0774
## COV       0.9500  0.9420  0.9360  0.9400  0.9500  0.9440

```

```
# compact table for paper
```

```
simsum(list(Uniform = simrandom100.3, BVN = simrandomBVN100.3))
```

```

## $Uniform
##      av.nCH      RB      RSE rRMSE      COV
## 1  121.062 -0.011 0.069 0.072 0.940
## 2  123.252 -0.015 0.068 0.073 0.932
## 3  126.322 -0.021 0.066 0.072 0.928
## 4  129.288 -0.025 0.065 0.072 0.900
## 1-4 124.758 -0.021 0.067 0.070 0.928
## 1,4 125.424 -0.020 0.067 0.071 0.938

```

```

## $BVN
##      av.nCH      RB      RSE rRMSE      COV
## 1  108.326  0.006 0.077 0.080 0.950
## 2  109.482  0.004 0.077 0.082 0.942
## 3  110.934 -0.001 0.077 0.081 0.936
## 4  112.054 -0.009 0.076 0.078 0.940
## 1-4 110.022 -0.003 0.077 0.078 0.950
## 1,4 109.982 -0.007 0.077 0.077 0.944

```

```
# spatial scale parameter
```

```

output <- simsum(list(Uniform = simrandom100.3, BVN = simrandomBVN100.3),
  component = 'pred', parm = 'sigma', compact = c("av.parmhat", "sd.parmhat"))
lapply(output, '/', 50) # in units of detector spacing

```

```

## $Uniform
##      av.parmhat sd.parmhat
## 1      0.59046  0.01422
## 2      0.65116  0.01836
## 3      0.74018  0.02470
## 4      0.82576  0.02966
## 1-4    0.70118  0.02356
## 1,4    0.71320  0.02736

```

```

## $BVN
##      av.parmhat sd.parmhat

```

```
## 1      0.50072    0.01780
## 2      0.55270    0.02558
## 3      0.62760    0.03130
## 4      0.69782    0.03806
## 1-4    0.59366    0.03278
## 1,4    0.60450    0.03652
```

Straight line 36-detectors

```
tr <- make.grid(36, 1, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simgridalignlinw1.1 <- vector('list', 6)
names(simgridalignlinw1.1) <- c(1:4, '1-4', '1,4')
simgridalignlinw4.1 <- simgridalignlinw3.1 <- simgridalignlinw2.1 <- simgridalignlinw1.1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN',
                CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  # bun perpendicular to traps
  args$theta <- 0; simgridalignlinw1.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bun oblique to traps
  args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignlinw2.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bun parallel to traps
  args$theta <- pi/2; simgridalignlinw3.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bun random orientation
  args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignlinw4.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignlinw1.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignlinw2.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/2; simgridalignlinw3.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignlinw4.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy2))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignlinw1.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignlinw2.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/2; simgridalignlinw3.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignlinw4.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

save(simgridalignlinw1.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw1.1.RData'))
save(simgridalignlinw2.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw2.1.RData'))
save(simgridalignlinw3.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw3.1.RData'))
save(simgridalignlinw4.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw4.1.RData'))

# compact table linear
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw1.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw2.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw3.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw4.1.RData'))
simsum(list(Perpendicular = simgridalignlinw1.1,
           Oblique       = simgridalignlinw2.1,
```

```

Parallel = simgridalignlinw3.1,
Random   = simgridalignlinw4.1))

```

```

## $Perpendicular
##   av.nCH   RB   RSE rRMSE   COV
## 1   56.452 0.011 0.171 0.179 0.944
## 2   66.474 0.867 0.159 0.926 0.052
## 3   70.976 1.447 0.161   NA 0.000
## 4   73.130 1.791 0.168   NA 0.000
## 1-4 67.740 1.008 0.160 1.057 0.008
## 1,4 64.686 0.643 0.167 0.710 0.206
##
## $Oblique
##   av.nCH   RB   RSE rRMSE   COV
## 1   56.452 0.011 0.171 0.179 0.944
## 2   59.770 0.262 0.168 0.337 0.718
## 3   64.032 0.619 0.162 0.674 0.206
## 4   67.228 0.942 0.157 0.987 0.022
## 1-4 61.960 0.423 0.167 0.483 0.468
## 1,4 61.666 0.402 0.168 0.475 0.488
##
## $Parallel
##   av.nCH   RB   RSE rRMSE   COV
## 1   56.452 0.011 0.171 0.179 0.944
## 2   46.480 -0.490 0.167 0.499 0.018
## 3   40.924 -0.661 0.163 0.664 0.000
## 4   37.206 -0.746 0.160 0.748 0.000
## 1-4 44.372 -0.578 0.166 0.583 0.000
## 1,4 46.732 -0.553 0.166 0.559 0.008
##
## $Random
##   av.nCH   RB   RSE rRMSE   COV
## 1   56.400 0.029 0.172 0.181 0.954
## 2   58.290 0.075 0.173 0.207 0.908
## 3   60.340 0.124 0.175 0.277 0.832
## 4   61.762 0.171 0.176 0.343 0.764
## 1-4 59.258 0.106 0.173 0.263 0.816
## 1,4 59.360 0.094 0.173 0.243 0.862

```

Hollow square 36 detectors

```

tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity', hollow = TRUE)
simgridalignsqw1.1 <- vector('list', 4) # 'w' for wide
names(simgridalignsqw1.1) <- 1:4
simgridalignsqw3.1 <- simgridalignsqw2.1 <- simgridalignsqw1.1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                 lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN',
                 CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  # bvn aligned to traps

```

```

args$theta <- 0; simgridalignsqw1.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
# bun oblique to traps
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignsqw2.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
# bun random orientation
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignsqw3.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignsqw1.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignsqw2.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignsqw3.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy2))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignsqw1.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignsqw2.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignsqw3.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

save(simgridalignsqw1.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw1.1.RData'))
save(simgridalignsqw2.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw2.1.RData'))
save(simgridalignsqw3.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw3.1.RData'))

# compact table square
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw1.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw2.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw3.1.RData'))
simsum(list(Aligned = simgridalignsqw1.1,
           Oblique = simgridalignsqw2.1,
           Random = simgridalignsqw3.1))

```

```

## $Aligned
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 55.580  0.021 0.166 0.177 0.958
## 2 55.792 -0.067 0.165 0.189 0.882
## 3 55.724 -0.191 0.165 0.248 0.658
## 4 55.220 -0.297 0.163 0.336 0.368
##
## $Oblique
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 55.580 0.021 0.166 0.177 0.958
## 2 58.794 0.198 0.168 0.284 0.800
## 3 62.406 0.421 0.171 0.513 0.492
## 4 65.362 0.616 0.175 0.733 0.306
##
## $Random
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 55.468 0.020 0.166 0.170 0.940
## 2 57.068 0.061 0.167 0.212 0.906
## 3 59.110 0.108 0.169 0.275 0.834
## 4 60.814 0.140 0.170 0.314 0.808

```

Reduced spacing (σ instead of 2σ)

10 x 10 grid

```
tr <- make.grid(10,10, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity')
simrandomBVNs100.1 <- vector('list', 4)
names(simrandomBVNs100.1) <- 1:4
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr, theta = NULL,
                D = 4, CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details, seed = 347,
                type = 'BVN', lambda = 0.4)
for (i in 1:4) {
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = 25/i^0.5, sigmaY = 25*i^0.5))
  simrandomBVNs100.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}
save(simrandomBVNs100.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVNs100.1.RData'))
```

Straight line

```
tr <- make.grid(36, 1, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity')
simgridalignlinw1.1 <- vector('list', 6)
names(simgridalignlinw1.1) <- c(1:4, '1-4', '1,4')
simgridalignlinw4.1 <- simgridalignlinw3.1 <- simgridalignlinw2.1 <- simgridalignlinw1.1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN', theta = 0,
                CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  # bvn perpendicular to traps
  args$theta <- 0; simgridalignlin1.3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bvn oblique to traps
  args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignlin2.3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bvn parallel to traps
  args$theta <- pi/2; simgridalignlin3.3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bvn random orientation
  args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignlin4.3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignlin1.3[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignlin2.3[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/2; simgridalignlin3.3[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignlin4.3[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy2))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignlin1.3[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignlin2.3[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/2; simgridalignlin3.3[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignlin4.3[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

save(simgridalignlin1.3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin1.3.RData'))
save(simgridalignlin2.3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin2.3.RData'))
```

```
save(simgridalignlin3.3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin3.3.RData'))
save(simgridalignlin4.3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin4.3.RData'))
```

Hollow square

```
tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity', hollow = TRUE)
simgridalignsq1.1 <- vector('list', 4) # 'w' for wide
names(simgridalignsq1.1) <- 1:4
simgridalignsq3.1 <- simgridalignsq2.1 <- simgridalignsq1.1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN',
                CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  # bvn aligned to traps
  args$theta <- 0; simgridalignsq1.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bvn oblique to traps
  args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignsq2.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  # bvn random orientation
  args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignsq3.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignsq1.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignsq2.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignsq3.1[[5]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = rs2xy2))
args$theta <- 0; simgridalignsq1.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4; simgridalignsq2.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL; simgridalignsq3.1[[6]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)

save(simgridalignsq1.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq1.2.RData'))
save(simgridalignsq2.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq2.2.RData'))
save(simgridalignsq3.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq3.2.RData'))
```

Spacing comparisons

10 x 10 grid

```
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVNs100.1.RData'))
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
simplot(list(BVN = simrandomBVNs100.1), legend = FALSE)
mtext(side=3, text = '25 m')
simplot(list(BVN = simrandomBVN100.3[1:4]), legend = FALSE)
mtext(side=3, text = '50 m')
```

Straight line

```

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin1.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin2.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin3.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin4.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw1.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw2.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw3.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlinw4.1.RData'))
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
simplot(list(Perpendicular = simgridalignlin1.3[1:4],
            Oblique       = simgridalignlin2.3[1:4],
            Parallel      = simgridalignlin3.3[1:4],
            Random        = simgridalignlin4.3[1:4]),
        legend = TRUE, ylim = c(-1,3.5))
mtext(side=3, text = '25 m')
simplot(list(Perpendicular = simgridalignlinw1.1[1:4],
            Oblique       = simgridalignlinw2.1[1:4],
            Parallel      = simgridalignlinw3.1[1:4],
            Random        = simgridalignlinw4.1[1:4]),
        legend = TRUE, ylim = c(-1,3.5))
mtext(side=3, text = '50 m')

```


Hollow square

```

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq1.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq2.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq3.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw1.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw2.1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsqw3.1.RData'))
par(mfrow =c(1,2))
simplot(list(Aligned = simgridalignsq1.2[1:4],
            Oblique = simgridalignsq2.2[1:4],

```

```

    Random = simgridalignsq3.2[1:4]),
  legend = TRUE, ylim = c(-1,3.5))
mtext(side=3, text = '25 m')
simplot(list(Aligned = simgridalignsqw1.1[1:4],
  Oblique = simgridalignsqw2.1[1:4],
  Random = simgridalignsqw3.1[1:4]),
  legend = TRUE, ylim = c(-1,3.5))
mtext(side=3, text = '50 m')

```


Variations

Low density (0.5/ha)

```

tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simrandom100low.2 <- vector('list', 4)
names(simrandom100low.2) <- 1:4
simrandomBVN100low.2 <- simrandom100low.2
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
  D = 0.5, CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  args$type <- 'uniform'; args$g0 <- 0.2
  simrandom100low.2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$type <- 'BVN'; args$lambda0 <- 0.4
  simrandomBVN100low.2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}
save(simrandom100low.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom100low.2.RData'))
save(simrandomBVN100low.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100low.2.RData'))

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom100low.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100low.2.RData'))

```

```
par(mfrow = c(1,1), mar = c(4,4,4,4), xpd = FALSE)
simplot(list(Uniform = simrandom100low.2, BVN = simrandomBVN100low.2),
  trueval = 0.5, legend = TRUE)
```



```
simsum(list(Uniform = simrandom100low.2, BVN = simrandomBVN100low.2),
  trueval = 0.5, compact = NULL)
```

```
## $Uniform
##           1           2           3           4
## av.npop    36.122   36.122   36.122   36.122
## av.nCH     15.310   15.488   15.906   16.318
## nvalid     500.000 500.000 500.000 500.000
## av.parmhat  0.502   0.498   0.497   0.495
## md.parmhat  0.495   0.496   0.499   0.497
## sd.parmhat  0.095   0.096   0.094   0.093
## RB         0.004  -0.003  -0.006  -0.009
## seRB       0.008   0.009   0.008   0.008
## RSE        0.196   0.194   0.190   0.186
## seRSE      0.001   0.001   0.001   0.001
## rRMSE      0.189   0.191   0.188   0.186
## COV        0.952   0.954   0.932   0.938
##
## $BVN
##           1           2           3           4
## av.npop    36.122   36.124   36.122   36.122
## av.nCH     13.630   13.722   13.904   14.072
## nvalid     500.000 499.000 500.000 500.000
## av.parmhat  0.513   0.513   0.507   0.505
## md.parmhat  0.509   0.505   0.504   0.497
```

## sd.parmhat	0.109	0.110	0.110	0.111
## RB	0.027	0.026	0.015	0.010
## seRB	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.010
## RSE	0.224	0.224	0.222	0.221
## seRSE	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
## rRMSE	0.219	NA	0.220	0.223
## COV	0.946	0.946	0.944	0.954

Small array (6 x 6 grid)

```
tr <- make.grid(6, 6, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simrandom36.2 <- vector('list', 4)
names(simrandom36.2) <- 1:4
simrandomBVN36.2 <- simrandom36.2
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
  D = 4, CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  args$type <- 'uniform'; args$g0 <- 0.2
  simrandom36.2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$type <- 'BVN'; args$lambda0 <- 0.4
  simrandomBVN36.2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}
save(simrandom36.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom36.2.RData'))
save(simrandomBVN36.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN36.2.RData'))

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom36.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN36.2.RData'))
par(mfrow = c(1,1), mar = c(4,4,4,4), xpd = FALSE)
simplot(list(Uniform = simrandom36.2[1:4], BVN = simrandomBVN36.2[1:4]), legend = TRUE)
```



```
simsum(list(Uniform = simrandom36.2, BVN = simrandomBVN36.2), compact = NULL)
```

```
## $Uniform
##           1           2           3           4           1-4           1,4
## av.npop    169.000  169.000  169.000  169.000  169.000  169.000
## av.nCH     49.310  50.536  52.198  53.946  50.890  51.102
## nvalid     500.000  500.000  500.000  500.000  500.000  500.000
## av.parmhat  3.986   3.972   3.954   3.963   3.912   3.927
## md.parmhat  3.979   3.951   3.939   3.943   3.901   3.937
## sd.parmhat  0.497   0.497   0.490   0.501   0.486   0.466
## RB         -0.004  -0.007  -0.011  -0.009  -0.022  -0.018
## seRB        0.006   0.006   0.005   0.006   0.005   0.005
## RSE         0.122   0.120   0.118   0.117   0.120   0.120
## seRSE       0.000   0.000   0.000   0.000   0.000   0.000
## rRMSE       0.124   0.124   0.123   0.126   0.123   0.118
## COV         0.944   0.942   0.952   0.928   0.942   0.956
##
## $BVN
##           1           2           3           4           1-4           1,4
## av.npop    169.000  169.000  169.000  169.000  169.000  169.000
## av.nCH     42.184  42.942  43.950  44.704  42.994  32.224
## nvalid     500.000  500.000  500.000  500.000  500.000  500.000
## av.parmhat  4.081   4.076   4.074   4.052   4.019   4.112
## md.parmhat  4.051   4.067   4.067   4.028   4.018   4.027
## sd.parmhat  0.593   0.581   0.569   0.565   0.573   0.837
## RB          0.020   0.019   0.019   0.013   0.005   0.028
## seRB        0.007   0.006   0.006   0.006   0.006   0.009
## RSE         0.140   0.139   0.139   0.139   0.139   0.202
## seRSE       0.000   0.000   0.000   0.000   0.000   0.001
```

```
## rRMSE      0.149  0.146  0.143  0.142  0.143  0.211
## COV       0.940  0.934  0.946  0.948  0.946  0.942
```

Common random orientation

```
tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simrandom100C.2 <- vector('list', 4)
names(simrandom100C.2) <- 1:4
simrandomBVN100C.2 <- simrandom100C.2
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                theta = -1, D = 4, CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HNN', details = details)
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  args$type <- 'uniform'; args$g0 <- 0.2
  simrandom100C.2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$type <- 'BVN'; args$lambda0 <- 0.4
  simrandomBVN100C.2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}
save(simrandom100C.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom100C.2.RData'))
save(simrandomBVN100C.2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100C.2.RData'))

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandom100C.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100C.2.RData'))
simplify(list(Uniform = simrandom100C.2, BVN = simrandomBVN100C.2), legend = TRUE)
```


Grid with varying orientation

Spacings narrow and wide (w); orientation parallel (p) and oblique(o). Only consider aspect ratio 4 for now.

```
tr <- make.grid(10,10, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity')
simrandomBVN100p.1 <- vector('list', 4)
names(simrandomBVN100p.1) <- 1:4
simrandomBVN100o.1 <- simrandomBVN100p.1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                type = 'BVN', lambda0 = 0.4,
                D = 4, CL = TRUE, detectfn = 'HHN', details = details)
for (i in 4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY, theta = 0))
  simrandomBVN100p.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY, theta = pi/4))
  simrandomBVN100o.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}

tr <- make.grid(10,10, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simrandomBVN100pw.1 <- vector('list', 4)
names(simrandomBVN100pw.1) <- 1:4
simrandomBVN100ow.1 <- simrandomBVN100pw.1
for (i in 4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY, theta = 0))
  simrandomBVN100pw.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY, theta = pi/4))
  simrandomBVN100ow.1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}

save(simrandomBVN100p.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100p.1.RData'))
save(simrandomBVN100o.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100o.1.RData'))

save(simrandomBVN100pw.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100pw.1.RData'))
save(simrandomBVN100ow.1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVN100ow.1.RData'))
```

Anisotropic model

Using function `anisotropic.fit`. Extract the fitted coefficients corresponding to `psiA` and `psiR` with the `coef` method for `secr` objects, and rely on direct estimation of density (`CL = FALSE`).

Hollow square

```
tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity', hollow = TRUE)
simaniso1 <- vector('list', 4); names(simaniso1) <- 1:4
simaniso4 <- simaniso3 <- simaniso2 <- simaniso1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN', CL = FALSE, detectfn = 'HHN',
                details = list(distribution = 'binomial'), extractfn = coef,
                secrfn = 'anisotropic.fit')
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
```

```

args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
args$theta <- 0      # aligned to detectors
simaniso1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4  # oblique to detectors
simaniso2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL  # random orientation
simaniso3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- -1    # common random orientation
simaniso4[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}
save(simaniso1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso1.RData'))
save(simaniso2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso2.RData'))
save(simaniso3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso3.RData'))
save(simaniso4, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso4.RData'))

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq1.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq2.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignsq3.2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simaniso4.RData'))
par(mfrow = c(1,2))
simplot(list(Aligned = simgridalignsq1.2[1:4],
            Oblique = simgridalignsq2.2[1:4],
            Random = simgridalignsq3.2[1:4]),
        ylim = c(-0.4,0.45), legend = TRUE, pchi = c(23, 22, 16))
text(-0.4, 0.5, 'a.', cex = 1.45, xpd = TRUE)
text(3, -0.35, 'isotropic')
simplot(list(Aligned = simaniso1,
            Oblique = simaniso2,
            Random = simaniso3),
        component = "pred",
        ylim = c(-0.4,0.45), legend = TRUE, pchi = c(23, 22, 16))
text(-0.4, 0.5, 'b.', cex = 1.45, xpd = TRUE)
text(3, -0.35, 'anisotropic')

```


Tabular summary for anisotropic model.

```
simsum(list(Aligned = simaniso1,
           Oblique = simaniso2,
           Random = simaniso3),
       component = "pred")
```

```
## $Aligned
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 34.428 -0.005 0.184 0.173 0.962
## 2 35.188 -0.009 0.186 0.168 0.970
## 3 36.572  0.000 0.186 0.165 0.968
## 4 37.898  0.018 0.182 0.171 0.970
##
## $Oblique
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 34.428 -0.005 0.184 0.173 0.962
## 2 36.468  0.020 0.196 0.191 0.960
## 3 39.392  0.041 0.200 0.221 0.936
## 4 41.842  0.058 0.197 0.228 0.938
##
## $Random
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 34.626  0.002 0.183 0.184 0.956
## 2 36.086  0.031 0.182 0.198 0.934
## 3 38.148  0.053 0.178 0.234 0.878
## 4 40.000  0.061 0.175 0.248 0.880
```

Tabular comparison of isotropic and anisotropic models for hollow grid.

```
tab1 <- simsum(list(Aligned = simgridalignsq1.2[1:4],
                  Oblique = simgridalignsq2.2[1:4],
                  Random = simgridalignsq3.2[1:4])) # find D-hat in the 'fit' component
tab2 <- simsum(list(Aligned = simaniso1,
                  Oblique = simaniso2,
```

```

        Random = simaniso3),
        component = "pred") # find D-hat in the 'pred' component
fn <- function(t1,t2) cbind(t1[,-1],t2[,-1])
mapply(fn, tab1, tab2, SIMPLIFY = FALSE)

```

```

## $Aligned
##      RB   RSE rRMSE  COV      RB   RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1  0.011 0.173 0.173 0.948 -0.005 0.184 0.173 0.962
## 2 -0.042 0.170 0.184 0.904 -0.009 0.186 0.168 0.970
## 3 -0.098 0.166 0.205 0.846  0.000 0.186 0.165 0.968
## 4 -0.136 0.162 0.239 0.754  0.018 0.182 0.171 0.970
##
## $Oblique
##      RB   RSE rRMSE  COV      RB   RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1  0.011 0.173 0.173 0.948 -0.005 0.184 0.173 0.962
## 2  0.118 0.170 0.229 0.884  0.020 0.196 0.191 0.960
## 3  0.222 0.166 0.337 0.728  0.041 0.200 0.221 0.936
## 4  0.281 0.163 0.402 0.636  0.058 0.197 0.228 0.938
##
## $Random
##      RB   RSE rRMSE  COV      RB   RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1  0.021 0.172 0.182 0.938  0.002 0.183 0.184 0.956
## 2  0.054 0.170 0.200 0.924  0.031 0.182 0.198 0.934
## 3  0.081 0.166 0.241 0.854  0.053 0.178 0.234 0.878
## 4  0.085 0.163 0.254 0.854  0.061 0.175 0.248 0.880

```

Straight line

```

tr <- make.grid(36, 1, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity')
simanisolin1 <- vector('list', 4); names(simanisolin1) <- 1:4
simanisolin5 <- simanisolin4 <- simanisolin3 <- simanisolin2 <- simanisolin1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN', CL = FALSE, detectfn = 'HHN',
                details = list(distribution = 'binomial'), extractfn = coef,
                secrfn = 'anisotropic.fit')
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  args$theta <- 0 # perpendicular to detectors
  simanisolin1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$theta <- pi/4 # oblique to detectors
  simanisolin2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$theta <- NULL # random orientation
  simanisolin3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$theta <- -1 # common random orientation
  simanisolin4[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$theta <- pi/2 # parallel
  simanisolin5[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args) # partial run 2018-08-23
}
save(simanisolin1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin1.RData'))
save(simanisolin2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin2.RData'))
save(simanisolin3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin3.RData'))

```

```
save(simanisolin4, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin4.RData'))
save(simanisolin5, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin5.RData'))
```

```
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin1.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin2.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simgridalignlin4.3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin1.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin2.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolin3.RData'))
par(mfrow = c(1,2))
simplot(list(Aligned = simgridalignlin1.3[1:4],
            Oblique = simgridalignlin2.3[1:4],
            Random = simgridalignlin4.3[1:4]),
        ylim = c(-1,3.5), legend = TRUE, pchi = c(23, 22, 16))
text(-0.1, 3.5, 'a.', cex = 1.45, xpd = TRUE)
text(1, -0.8, 'isotropic', adj=0)
simplot(list(Perpendicular = simanisolin1,
            Oblique = simanisolin2,
            Random = simanisolin3),
        component = "pred",
        ylim = c(-1,3.5), legend = TRUE, pchi = c(23, 22, 16))
text(-0.1, 3.5, 'b.', cex = 1.45, xpd = TRUE)
text(1, -0.8, 'anisotropic', adj=0)
```


Conclude that anisotropic transformation largely ineffective with linear array.

10 x 10 grid

```
tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 25, detector = 'proximity')
simanisogrid1 <- vector('list', 4); names(simanisogrid1) <- 1:4
simanisogrid4 <- simanisogrid3 <- simanisogrid2 <- simanisogrid1
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
```

```

        lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN', CL = FALSE, detectfn = 'HHN',
        details = list(distribution = 'binomial'), extractfn = coef,
        secrfn = 'anisotropic.fit')
for (i in 1:4) {
  sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
  args <- c(baseargs, list(sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY))
  args$theta <- 0      # aligned to detectors
  simanisogrid1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$theta <- pi/4  # oblique to detectors
  simanisogrid2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$theta <- NULL  # random orientation
  simanisogrid3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
  args$theta <- -1    # common random orientation
  simanisogrid4[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
}
save(simanisogrid1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogrid1.RData'))
save(simanisogrid2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogrid2.RData'))
save(simanisogrid3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogrid3.RData'))
save(simanisogrid4, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogrid4.RData'))

load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogrid3.RData'))
load(file = paste0(simfolder, 'simrandomBVNs100.1.RData'))
simsum(list(Simple = simrandomBVNs100.1))
simsum(list(Anisotropic = simanisogrid3), component = "pred")

```

```

## $Simple
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 41.016 -0.005 0.134 0.140 0.932
## 2 42.202 -0.012 0.132 0.139 0.920
## 3 44.010 -0.018 0.128 0.135 0.920
## 4 46.130 -0.011 0.124 0.132 0.928
##
## $Anisotropic
##   av.nCH    RB    RSE rRMSE  COV
## 1 41.468  0.001 0.134 0.136 0.942
## 2 42.604 -0.007 0.132 0.129 0.948
## 3 44.550 -0.008 0.128 0.127 0.938
## 4 46.508 -0.007 0.125 0.124 0.940

```

Performs well with full grid data (narrow spacing).

Now run all geometries with wide spacing (w) for aspect ratio 4.0.

```

tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simanisogridw1 <- vector('list', 4); names(simanisogridw1) <- 1:4
simanisogridw3 <- simanisogridw2 <- simanisogridw1
i <- 4
sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
  lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN', CL = FALSE, detectfn = 'HHN',
  details = list(distribution = 'binomial'), extractfn = coef,
  secrfn = 'anisotropic.fit', sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY)
args <- c(baseargs, list(theta = 0)) # aligned to detectors
simanisogridw1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4 # oblique to detectors

```

```

simanisogridw2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL # random orientation
simanisogridw3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
save(simanisogridw1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogridw1.RData'))
save(simanisogridw2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogridw2.RData'))
save(simanisogridw3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisogridw3.RData'))

tr <- make.grid(36, 1, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity')
simanisolinw1 <- vector('list', 4); names(simanisolinw1) <- 1:4
simanisolinw4 <- simanisolinw3 <- simanisolinw2 <- simanisolinw1
args <- c(baseargs, list(theta = 0)) # perpendicular to detectors
simanisolinw1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4 # oblique to detectors
simanisolinw2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/2 # parallel to detectors
simanisolinw3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL # random orientation
simanisolinw4[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
save(simanisolinw1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolinw1.RData'))
save(simanisolinw2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolinw2.RData'))
save(simanisolinw3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolinw3.RData'))
save(simanisolinw4, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisolinw4.RData'))

tr <- make.grid(10, 10, spacing = 50, detector = 'proximity', hollow = TRUE)
simanisow1 <- vector('list', 4); names(simanisow1) <- 1:4
simanisow3 <- simanisow2 <- simanisow1
i <- 4
sigmaX <- 25/i^0.5; sigmaY <- 25*i^0.5
baseargs <- list(nrepl = nrepl, buffer = 200, ncores = ncores, traps = tr,
                lambda0 = 0.4, D = 4, type = 'BVN', CL = FALSE, detectfn = 'HHN',
                details = list(distribution = 'binomial'), extractfn = coef,
                secrfn = 'anisotropic.fit', sigmaX = sigmaX, sigmaY = sigmaY)
args <- c(baseargs, list(theta = 0)) # aligned to detectors
simanisow1[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- pi/4 # oblique to detectors
simanisow2[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
args$theta <- NULL # random orientation
simanisow3[[i]] <- do.call(runEllipseSim, args)
save(simanisow1, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisow1.RData'))
save(simanisow2, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisow2.RData'))
save(simanisow3, file = paste0(simfolder, 'simanisow3.RData'))

```